

Supplementary Figure S1

Supplementary Figure S1: Leave-biobank-out meta-analysis vs biobank effects of the index variants for loci identified in this study. In each case index variants with strong signal way above the genome-wide threshold all-biobank meta-analysis (p -value $< 10^{-10}$) for the regression.

Supplementary Figure S2

Supplementary Figure S2: QQ plot for the GBMI POAG meta-analysis of all individuals. The meta-analysis included a total of 26,848 cases and 1,460,599 controls from 15 global biobanks across six ancestries.

Supplementary Figure S3

Supplementary Figure S3: QQ plot for the GBMI POAG meta-analysis of female individuals. The meta-analysis was across 9 biobanks in 7,916 cases and 269,105 controls.

Supplementary Figure S4

Supplementary Figure S4: QQ plot for the GBMI POAG meta-analysis of male individuals. The meta-analysis was across 10 biobanks in 9,538 cases and 342,870 controls.

Supplementary Figure S5

Supplementary Figure S5: The number of independent POAG GWAS hits ($p < 5e-8$) and loci for each biobank contributing to GBMI.

Supplementary Figure S6

Supplementary Figure S6: Correlation of SNP effect size estimates between non-Finnish European and African ancestry in GBMI dataset. The x-axis shows effect estimates in beta scale for the independent genome-wide significant loci obtained from the European GBMI for POAG. The y-axis shows the effect estimates in beta scale for the same SNPs obtained from the African GBMI dataset.

Supplementary Figure S7

Supplementary Figure S7: Correlation of SNP effect size estimates between non-Finnish European and Asian ancestry in GBMI dataset. The x-axis shows effect estimates in beta scale for the independent genome-wide significant loci obtained from the European GBMI for POAG. The y-axis shows the effect estimates in beta scale for the same SNPs obtained from Asian GBMI dataset.

Supplementary Figure S8

Supplementary Figure S8: Correlation of SNP effect size estimates between African and Asian ancestry in GBMI dataset. The x-axis shows effect estimates in beta scale for the independent genome-wide significant loci obtained from the African GBMI for POAG. The y-axis shows the effect estimates in beta scale for the same SNPs obtained from Asian GBMI dataset.

Supplementary Figure S9

Supplementary Figure S9: Sex-specific loci and significant loci in the combined both sex meta-analysis that show differential signal between the two sexes. -p= p-values; -Het p-value= Heterogeneity test p-value.

Supplementary Figure S10

Supplementary Figure S10: Sex difference in effect of proxy rs1741032 variant in expression of CELSR2 gene in GTEx muscle skeletal. p-values (p) are based on ANOVA tests.

Supplementary Figure S11

Supplementary Figure S11: QQ plot for the GBMI-IGGC-GGLAD POAG meta-analysis. This was meta-analysis that include GBMI (n=1,259,040), International Glaucoma Genetics Consortium (IGGC) of European ancestry (n=192,702) and Genetics of Glaucoma in People of African Descent (GGLAD) (n=26,295) datasets.

Supplementary Figure S12

Supplementary Figure S12: Manhattan plots for the cross-ancestry GBMI-IGGC-GGLAD POAG meta-analysis. Each dot represents a SNP, the x-axis shows the chromosomes where each SNP is located, and the y-axis shows $-\log_{10}$ P-value of the association of each SNP with POAG across-ancestry meta-GBMI. The nearest gene to the most significant SNP in each locus is reported. Novel loci are labeled in red and those identified in GBMI but fall below genome-wide threshold in GBMI-IGGC-GGLAD meta-analysis are labeled in green. The red horizontal line shows the genome-wide significant threshold (P-value = $5e-8$; $-\log_{10}$ P-value = 7.30). Details of each genome-wide significant hit are in Suppl. Table S7

Supplementary Figure S13: A circular-Manhattan plot showing the POAG TWAS significant gene signals (threshold p value < 2.5e-6, marked with a dashed red line in each ring) identified by the PrediXcan, JTI, and UTMOST models in 23 GTX tissues. The circles from the innermost to outermost represent: the Manhattan plot of PrediXcan, JTI, UTMOST, chromosome numbers (each one with different color) and genes identified by the models. Numbers in parentheses correspond with locus#index in Suppl. Table S7. Each genome-wide significant gene signal is represented as a colored triangle. More details are reported in Supplementary Table S12 and S13.

Supplementary Figure S14

Supplementary Figure S14: Prediction performance of the leave-biobank-out GBMI, GBMI-IGGC-GGLAD, and IGGC POAG meta-analysis as source GWAS. The prediction performance was estimated by R² on the liability scale in BioVU and Lifelines biobanks with all samples and case control ratio of ~1:4. GLGS is a traditional case control cohort with best phenotyping and represents a homogenous POAG case set.